

INTEGRATING COMPUTER VISION INTO EQUIPMENT MAINTENANCE AT CHU-UFPA

Silvana da Costa Oliveira
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e
Biomédica
Universidade Federal do Pará
Belém, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0004-3628-4612

Valdemir Rodrigues da Luz
Setor de Engenharia Clínica
Hospital Universitário João de Barros
Barreto
Belém, Brazil

Ana Carolina Q. S. Müller
Faculdade de Engenharia Elétrica e
Biomédica
Universidade Federal do Pará
Belém, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0001-6664-9847

Abstract— This study applies computer vision techniques to detect defects in printed circuit boards of multiparameter monitors and pulmonary ventilators, in order to reduce corrective maintenance. Using transfer learning and data augmentation, the model achieved 77.77% accuracy, despite limited real data.

Keywords — Computer vision. Corrective maintenance. Multiparameter monitors.

I. INTRODUCTION

The constant technological evolution in healthcare has resulted in a significant increase in the complexity of medical and hospital equipment (MHE), which are vital components for the prevention, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation of diseases, ensuring the safety of patients and users.

Effective maintenance of these devices is crucial to ensuring their availability, minimizing failures and optimizing patient care quality, as well as protecting healthcare personnel from work-related accidents. Historically, the healthcare sector has relied on traditional maintenance approaches, such as corrective maintenance (CM), which focuses on correcting errors after a failure, and preventive maintenance (PM), which performs periodic activities without considering the current condition of the equipment, often resulting in unnecessary costs by replacing parts before the end of their useful life [1]. However, traditional maintenance strategies no longer meet the growing demands of modern healthcare organizations. Maintenance failures can cause disruptions in healthcare services and put patients' lives at risk.

Statistics from the World Health Organization (WHO) indicate that more than 80% of medical equipment failures are caused by preventable reasons, with inadequate maintenance accounting for approximately 60% of these incidents [1]. Given this scenario, the integration of information technologies, Big Data, and Machine Learning (ML) techniques has emerged as a promising way to improve healthcare services. In this context, Predictive Maintenance (PdM) has gained prominence. Unlike traditional approaches, PdM focuses on predicting equipment failures by continuously collecting data in real time and processing these data to detect errors and anticipate defects. This strategy allows improvement of the maintenance activity decision making process, mainly by avoiding downtime [2] [3], which contributes to reducing maintenance costs, increasing the functional activity of devices without

failures and, consequently, improving the quality of healthcare. Although widely used in other industries, such as manufacturing, energy and aerospace, the adoption of PdM in the medical field is still in its early stages and faces several obstacles.

This paper addresses this gap, focusing on the development of a system for the automatic detection of faults and anomalies in medical and hospital equipment. The project focuses specifically on inspecting the printed circuit boards (PCBs) of critical equipment such as multiparameter monitors and mechanical ventilators at the João de Barros Barreto University Hospital (HUIBB). The methodology employed involves the application of Computer Vision (CV) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, with an emphasis on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which are widely recognized for their pattern recognition capabilities and high accuracy in image classification. The main objective is to develop a computer vision-based system capable of identifying anomalies in PCBs, making equipment maintenance more effective and contributing to efficiency in equipment management. The initial stages of the project included an in-depth literature review, the collection of real images of PCBs (both under normal and defective conditions), and the development of a preliminary CNN model. The goal is for this system to be integrated into the hospital maintenance flow, offering continuous and predictive monitoring that minimizes failures, extends equipment life and increases patient safety.

II. PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE

Predictive maintenance has emerged as an essential strategy in the management of MHEs, seeking not only to optimize operating costs, but also to strengthen organizational competitiveness. Its application helps to guarantee the availability, reliability, and safety of equipment. Unlike corrective maintenance, which is triggered only after failures occur, and preventive maintenance, which follows fixed intervention schedules, PdM is based on continuous collection of data via sensors and the application of analytical techniques, making it possible to predict failures and schedule interventions more efficiently. This reduces unexpected downtime and extends the useful life of machines [4].

The effective implementation of a PdM system requires a multidisciplinary effort that ranges from the acquisition and preprocessing of signals in the plant to their analysis and storage, thus requiring knowledge across several areas [5].

In the healthcare context, the application of predictive maintenance is still in its infancy, despite its numerous potential benefits, such as reducing maintenance costs, increasing the reliability of medical equipment and, above all, raising the level of patient safety. The adoption of this approach, however, faces additional barriers due to the operational complexity and rigor of area-specific regulations, as well as the inherent sensitivity of clinical data [1].

III. CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are widely used for pattern recognition in images, applying convolutional filters to extract relevant features and classify elements with high precision [6]. Their effectiveness stems from a specialized architecture inspired by the organization of the human visual cortex, where neurons respond to stimuli in restricted regions of the visual field, known as the receptive field [7]. This structure allows CNNs to capture spatial and temporal dependencies in images, overcoming limitations present in fully connected networks, which treat all pixels equivalently and require the spatial structure of the data to be inferred during training. Unlike methods that require manual filters, CNNs can automatically learn discriminative characteristics from the data, with less need for preprocessing [7].

The architecture of CNNs is based on three fundamental ideas: local receptive fields, shared weights and pooling [6]. Shared weights allow the same set of parameters to be applied to different locations in the image, drastically reducing the number of parameters to be learned and memory requirements, while increasing the statistical efficiency of the model [7]. Pooling, in turn, reduces the resolution of the feature map, making the network less sensitive to small variations in position or distortions and helping to prevent overfitting [6]. The introduction of non-linear activation functions, such as the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), is crucial for increasing the non-linearity of the network, allowing the recognition of complex patterns and mitigating the problem of the vanishing gradient that affects other functions such as the sigmoid [8]. These advances have made CNNs indispensable tools in image recognition and catalysts for progress in deep learning [9].

In the study by Lee et al. [10], the application of CNNs combined with Class Activation Maps (CAM) was proposed for the diagnosis of surface defects in steel, achieving an accuracy of 99.44%. The method demonstrated superior performance compared to traditional machine learning algorithms, such as Support Vector Machines (SVM) and logistic regression. It also offered interpretability by highlighting the most relevant regions of the images for decision-making. Adapting this approach to the context of medical equipment suggests that using CNNs can significantly improve the accuracy of anomaly detection, making equipment maintenance more effective.

Fig. 1. Example of a defective image of a DIXTAL mechanical fan. The defective component is highlighted in red.

Fig. 2. Example of a non-defective image of a Bionet multiparameter monitor.

A. Image Acquisition

Computer vision enables more efficient and accurate anomaly detection than human visual inspection of equipment. The process involves capturing images of the devices, preprocessing them to improve quality, extracting features, and performing image classification. The availability of a large number of samples representative of the targeted issue is a key factor in the success of automatic inspection.

Multiparameter monitors are essential medical devices commonly found in hospitals and clinics. They continuously measure and display multiple vital signs—such as heart rate, blood pressure, and oxygen saturation on a single interface. These monitors play a critical role in patient care, and their use is especially crucial in intensive care units, emergency rooms, and operating theaters, where rapid decision-making is vital.

In real-world applications, a significant challenge is the limited availability of monitors for photography, which was

experienced during the present work. Clinical sectors lacked spare units, preventing the temporary removal of equipment for image recording. Moreover, most accessible devices were fully functional, with no visible PCB faults, which made it difficult to obtain examples of defects.

To address this limitation, an alternative strategy was adopted: expanding the database to include images of mechanical ventilators, which showed a higher incidence of PCB defects. Mechanical ventilators are critical life-support devices used to assist or replace spontaneous breathing in patients who cannot breathe adequately on their own. It increased the number of defective samples, improving the representativeness of the training data. From the multiparameter monitors, there are 19 defective and 41 non-defective images, while the mechanical ventilators contributed an additional 59 images (56 defective and 03 non-defective). Although the dataset remains small, it is sufficient for a proof-of-concept test for the present proposal.

Figures 1 and 2 show sample images from each class in the dataset, defective and non-defective, respectively. In particular, Figure 1 highlights the defective region of the PCB with a red square, corresponding to the sound module component. This example illustrates the complexity of the present proposal, when a defect in a PCB may consist of a single faulty component among hundreds of others, often with minimal visual differences.

B. Preprocessing

The original dataset was divided into two classes: “defective” and “non-defective”. To train the model, 70% of the images in each class were allocated to the training set, while the remaining 30% made up the validation set. This division sought to ensure a sufficient number of samples for validation, avoiding an imbalance between the stages of the learning process.

The images, initially with a resolution of 4032×3024 pixels, were resized to 512×512 pixels, compatible with the tested architectures. Also, this reduction in image size contributed to reducing the computational cost while ensuring the quality and representativeness of the problem.

C. Data Augmentation

To improve the model’s ability to generalize, random transformations were applied exclusively to the images in the training set. The modifications included: rotation of up to 30° , horizontal and vertical translation, shear, zoom, and horizontal flip. These modifications help reduce the risk of overfitting and improve the model’s ability to generalize to new images, making it more robust [9].

D. CNN Architectures

Custom CNN

A convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture was implemented for the image classification task proposed in

this study. The architecture consists of three convolutional layers followed by activation functions and pooling layers to progressively reduce spatial dimensions, while preserving essential features. These layers are then connected to one fully connected (dense) layer (128 neurons), responsible for the classification based on the learned features. To prevent overfitting, regularization techniques such as dropout were also incorporated. The network loss function was optimized using a gradient-based optimizer. The final layer uses a sigmoid activation function for binary classification.

The model was implemented using TensorFlow, and its performance was evaluated through accuracy and loss on both training and validation sets.

EfficientNetV2L model

The EfficientNetV2L architecture was chosen for its computational efficiency and high performance with fewer parameters, which makes it ideal for applications with limited computational resources. According to Zhao et al. [11], EfficientNetV2 has demonstrated excellent results in image classification tasks with hardware constraints, such as corrosion detection, where it is necessary to preserve accuracy without compromising system performance. The model was conceived based on the idea that an appropriate balance between network depth, width, and resolution can maximize performance, as demonstrated by Tan and Le. [12], being up to 6.8 times smaller than previous architectures, without detriment to accuracy.

EfficientNetV2 is an evolution of EfficientNetV1, with improvements in training time and scalability, using techniques such as progressive learning. This strategy allows models to be trained more quickly and efficiently, gradually adjusting the image resolution and the level of regularization.

The EfficientNetV2L architecture is made up of several optimized convolution blocks (MBConv and Fused-MBConv), and its depth includes dozens of convolutional layers that work by gradually extracting increasingly complex features from the input image. After the convolutional extractions, a Global Average Pooling layer is applied, which, as observed by Zhao et al. [11], has better performance in terms of accuracy and stability of the validation curves when compared to Global Max Pooling. In addition to reducing data dimensionality, this layer contributes significantly to mitigating overfitting by eliminating the need for multiple densely connected parameters.

E. Transfer Learning

The transfer learning technique was used with the EfficientNetV2L model, loading the pre-trained weights into ImageNet. This approach makes it possible to reuse the knowledge acquired by the model on a large generalist dataset, applying it to a specific task with fewer samples [13]. To adapt the model to the new problem, almost all the layers of EfficientNetV2L were frozen, except for the last 20, which remained trainable. This strategy made it possible to preserve the network’s general knowledge base and focus

the adjustment on the deeper levels, which deal with more specific patterns.

In addition, a new classification head was added consisting of a Global Average Pooling layer, a dense layer with 128 neurons and ReLU activation, a dropout layer with a rate of 50%, and, finally, an output layer with sigmoid activation, responsible for the binary prediction between the “defective” and “non-defective” classes.

With this configuration, the final model had a total of 117,910,945 parameters, of which 110,725,888 remained frozen and 7,185,057 were trained. This proportion demonstrates the reduced computational impact of the approach, since only around 6.1% of the parameters require updating during training, maintaining efficiency and reducing the risk of overfitting in a scenario with a limited database.

Fig. 3 illustrates the proposed workflow for the anomaly detection. The diagram highlights the sequential stages, starting with the acquisition of images from multiparameter monitors and mechanical ventilators, followed by preprocessing and data augmentation procedures. These steps prepare the dataset for the classification phase, performed with CNN-based architectures, which enable the automatic detection of defective components.

Fig. 3. Diagram of the process stages.

F. CNN Training Strategy

Both networks were trained for 20 epochs using a batch size of 32 samples. These values were empirically set, as no significant performance improvements were observed beyond this point. The relatively small batch size was chosen to optimize memory and processing usage, allowing more frequent updates of neural network weights, balancing convergence speed and stability, and achieving greater data

accuracy [14] [15].

The early stopping method was used, which stops training when the validation loss (val_loss) stops improving after a certain number of epochs. The optimizer adopted was Adam, configured with a default learning rate of 0.001. The metric used to evaluate the model’s learning during training was the accuracy over the training set, as it is a direct measure of performance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of a CNN-based anomaly detection algorithm revealed significant challenges primarily due to the limitations of our real-world dataset. Initially, the model trained “from scratch” with this dataset achieved an accuracy of just 61.11%. While this is above the chance level (50%) in a binary classification context, it proved insufficient for applications in predictive maintenance of medical equipment, underscoring the inherent complexity of our original database.

It’s important to highlight that the collection and utilization of an entirely original dataset of defective PCBs from medical and hospital equipment is a central, and challenging, aspect of this work. The difficulty in obtaining such data, stemming from the scarcity of monitors and ventilators available for photography and the predominance of functional devices in clinical settings, underscores the intrinsic value of each sample in our dataset.

The custom CNN, when trained with the real dataset augmented experienced an increment of accuracy by 3%, approximately. Still, insufficient to configure as an automatic framework for medical equipment inspection.

The importance of sample volume and variety for the generalization of deep learning models is further reinforced by comparing our performance with the “The Oxford IIIT Pet” benchmark dataset, where the custom model achieved 98.82% of accuracy. This contrast highlights the complexity and uniqueness of our real-world dataset.

Applying transfer learning using the EfficientNetV2L model retrained on the real dataset did not yield significantly better results than the previous test, achieving an accuracy of 66.66% (fewer than 5 additional samples correctly classified).

When combining both TF and DA, the EfficientNetV2L achieved 77.77% of train accuracy. This improvement demonstrates the effectiveness of reusing pretrained weights from large databases and artificially diversifying the dataset, especially in scenarios with limited data [16] [17].

TABLE 1. Comparison between models

Model	Accuracy
Custom CNN with benchmark dataset	98.82%
Custom CNN with real dataset	61.11%
Custom CNN with real dataset+DA	63.88%
EfficientNetV2L+TL+real dataset	66.66%
EfficientNetV2L+TL+real dataset+DA	77.77%

Table 1 summarizes this comparison, highlighting the

performance gain (from 61.11% to 77.77%) provided by transfer learning and data augmentation. It can also be seen that, when used in isolation, both strategies did not result in satisfactory classifications. This emphasizes the model's adaptability when initialized with feature-rich representations learned in data-abundant domains [7].

Figure 4 illustrates the accuracy and loss curves for the training and validation phases of the transfer learning model (EfficientNetV2L+TL+real dataset+DA in Table 1). It can be observed that over 20 epochs, despite minor fluctuations, both curves converge steadily with no obvious signs of overfitting. This indicates that the model was able to learn relevant patterns even with the limited number of images, benefiting from the representations previously extracted by EfficientNetV2L. The proximity between the training and validation curves suggests that the model is generalizing reasonably well, confirming the effectiveness of the adopted strategy.

(a) Training and validation loss curves.

(b) Training and validation accuracy curves.

Fig. 4. Training and validation curves for transfer learning model. (a) Loss curves. (b) Accuracy curves.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated the significant potential of computer vision and deep learning for automated fault detection in PCBs of medical and hospital equipment. Despite the inherent challenges posed by a limited and unique real-world dataset, the present approach yielded promising results.

Initially, a model trained from scratch achieved an accuracy of 61.11%. While exceeding the random chance level, this performance was insufficient for critical applications. By strategically implementing data augmentation and transfer learning with the EfficientNetV2L architecture, the accuracy was improved to 77.77%. This gain underscores the effectiveness of leveraging pretrained knowledge and artificially expanding data diversity in scenarios with scarce real-world samples. The contrast with the 98.82% accuracy on a benchmark dataset further emphasizes the crucial role of data volume and variety in model generalization.

While the current accuracy of 77.77% indicates room for further enhancement, these findings confirm the viability of integrating this system into hospital maintenance workflows. Future work will focus on systematically expanding the real PCB image database, particularly with diverse defect types. Additionally, experimenting with other pretrained architectures, more refined hyperparameter settings, and applying selective fine-tuning methods could contribute to further performance gains.

This research represents an initial step towards enhancing operational efficiency and patient safety through advanced predictive maintenance in healthcare

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the support of the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) through the provision of a scholarship during the development of this project. The authors also thank the Clinical Engineering Sector (SEC) of the João de Barros Barreto University Hospital (HJBB) for their collaboration and availability, which were essential to the execution of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. Manchadi, F-E. Ben-Bouazza, and B. Jioudi, "Predictive maintenance in healthcare system: A survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 61313–61330, 2023.
- [2] J. Lee, E. Lapira, B. Bagheri, and H. an Kao, "Recent advances and trends in predictive manufacturing

- systems in big data environment,” *Manufacturing Letters*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 38–41, 2013.
- [3] E. Sezer, D. Romero, F. Guedea, M. Macchi, and C. Emmanouilidis, “An industry 4.0-enabled low cost predictive maintenance approach for smes,” in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE/ITMC)*, pp. 1–8, 2018.
- [4] P. Nunes, J. Santos, and E. Rocha, “Challenges in predictive maintenance – a review,” *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, vol. 40, pp. 53–67, 2023.
- [5] T. Zonta, C. A. da Costa, R. da Rosa Righi, M. J. de Lima, E. S. da Trindade, and G. P. Li, “Predictive maintenance in the industry 4.0: A systematic literature review,” *Computers Industrial Engineering*, vol. 150, p. 106889, 2020.
- [6] Y. Lecun and Y. Bengio, “Convolutional networks for images, speech, and time-series,” 01 1995.
- [7] I. Goodfellow, Y. Bengio, and A. Courville, *Deep Learning*. MIT Press, 2016. <http://www.deeplearningbook.org>.
- [8] J. Wu, “Introduction to convolutional neural networks,” 05 2017.
- [9] L. Alzubaidi, J. Zhang, A. J. Humaidi, A. Al-Dujaili, Y. Duan, O. Al-Shamma, J. Santamariaacute;a, M. A. Fadhel, M. Al-Amidie, and L. Farhan, “Review of deep learning: Concepts, cnn architectures, challenges, applications, future directions,” *Journal of Big Data*, 03 2021.
- [10] S. Y. Lee, B. A. Tama, S. J. Moon, and S. Lee, “Steel surface defect diagnostics using deep convolutional neural network and class activation map,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 24, 2019.
- [11] Z. Zhao, E. Bakar, N. Razak, and M. N. Akhtar, “Corrosion image classification method based on efficientnetv2,” *Heliyon*, vol. 10, p. e36754, 08 2024.
- [12] M. Tan and Q. Le, “Efficientnetv2: Smaller models and faster training,” in *Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on Machine Learning* (M. Meila and T. Zhang, eds.), vol. 139 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pp. 10096–10106, PMLR, 18–24 Jul 2021.
- [13] S. Tulasi Krishna and H. k. Kalluri, “Deep learning and transfer learning approaches for image classification,” 06 2019.
- [14] D. Masters and C. Luschi, “Revisiting small batch training for deep neural networks,” 2018.
- [15] I. Kandel and M. Castelli, “The effect of batch size on the generalizability of the convolutional neural networks on a histopathology dataset,” *ICT Express*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 312–315, 2020.
- [16] K.-T. Shorten, C., “A survey on image data augmentation for deep learning,” *Journal of Big Data*, 07 2019.
- [17] E. Elyan, P. Vuttipittayamongkol, P. Johnston, K. Martin, K. McPherson, C. F. Moreno-García, C. Jayne, and M. M. K. Sarker, “Computer vision and machine learning for medical image analysis: recent advances, challenges, and way forward,” *Artificial Intelligence Surgery*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2022.